

THEORETICAL BASICS OF THE TYPES OF MUSICAL ACTIVITIES IN PRIMARY CLASS MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

Karimova Dildora Anvarovna

Associate Professor of Tashkent State Pedagogical
University named after Nizami

Yusupov Yusupboy Mansurbek ugli

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami
Master's student of "Music education and art direction"

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10824464>

Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the scientific theoretical characteristics of the musical abilities of elementary school students in music culture classes.

Key words: Primary education, music culture, musical ability, scientific analysis, scientific approach.

Introduction.

It is important to develop musical abilities of students in general secondary schools, to increase their effectiveness, because they are serious about independent activities and determining their life goals according to their age characteristics.

Teaching students to be creative and solve problems independently in music lessons is an important factor in increasing educational efficiency. As long as this is the case, the educational process should be organized in such a way that the students become equal partners of the teacher in the educational process, instead of being the object of the educational process.

In the development of our national spirituality, music plays an important role in teaching students to creative activities. It is one of the oldest and, at the same time, areas of the national music art, widespread among the people and deeply embedded in their life. Music also reflects reality. The influence of music on our national spirituality is so great that science has already proved that it is possible to cure patients with its help.

Abu Ali Ibn Sina attached great importance to the influence of music and put forward the idea that some mental illnesses can be treated with the help of music.

The great philosopher Abu Nasr Farabi expressed his valuable opinions about the types of melodies in music theory, their origins, and their spiritual and spiritual impact on a person in the book "*Great Music*". Farabi was not only a theoretician in musicology, but also a practitioner. He himself gained fame as a well-known musician, a great musician and composer, and an inventor of a new

musical instrument. Reflecting on the wonderful magical power and miraculous effect of music, Farabi says in his work "*On the Origin of Sciences*": This science is useful in the sense that it brings a person who has lost his balance to order, He perfects the people who have not reached perfection and keeps their balance.

In particular, creative activity in national culture opens up the world of high feelings, pleasure and exciting ideas. It makes people spiritually rich and perfect.

A child can feel music even when he does not know how to hold a pencil or read and write. Often, these first impressions affect the formation of attitudes towards music. Therefore, in the main areas of reform of general education schools, attention is also paid to music education. Music, first of all, softens children's emotions. It awakens many human qualities in them, like the feeling of musical works. Of course, literature, history, sports, and other fields play an important role in the development of human qualities. Therefore, poetry and music always live side by side. It is born under the influence of nature, moreover, it is formed in kindergarten and school. Music lessons educate students not only in terms of sophistication, but also in a broad sense, morally and spiritually. It would be good if our songs, songs, and statuses, which are passed down from generation to generation, endure the ravages of time, and embody the dreams, thoughts, and aspirations of the people, get a wider place in the programs of all kinds of schools and pedagogical institutes.

Music can soften a person's heart, awaken feelings of love and compassion that indicate faith. At the same time, in the content of statuses, the task of artistic expression of the ideas of Sufism in accordance with the ideology of the great state is also set. Naturally, the research of these complex scientific issues is entrusted to fully mature musicologists.

Human education and development has been one of the most urgent problems of any society. Because the formation, development, prosperity of the society depends on the education in this society. The fact that music is studied in connection with speech art and literature makes a great contribution to the development of the name and practice of music.

Improving the musical education of students through creative activities in personal development is definitely directly dependent on the educational methodology. The methodology of music education belongs to the system as a science and has its own independent place. This subject studies its laws in order to further improve the content and methods of music education methodology. The methodology of music education is based on the generalized experiences of the sciences of sophistication, musicology, physiology, and psychology in

educational institutions. The methodology of music education is inextricably linked with the sciences of musicology. If the name of refinement forms the basis of its methodology, it directly affects the content and methods of education.

The essence of the methodology of music education is important for the young generation, where the art and culture of music is growing. The development of methodology as a science is directly related to the improvement of education and the art of music in society. Together with these, he puts forward the general principles of the methodology of music education. These principles have the principles of artistic and technical development of consciousness, these principles are aimed at developing the students' musical ability, increasing their interest in music, and cultivating artistry.

Conscious perception of a musical work helps students to engage in creative activities, to discover the content of the work, and to gather musical experiences and enrich their spiritual world. The principle of emotional awareness of music education develops the ability to correctly evaluate the listening work through the increase of harmony: their taste is cultivated in their interest in music. The principle of artistic and technical stage requires qualified personnel for artistic and expressive performance of the work. Pays attention to students' acquisition of singing skills. As a result of students' formation of ideas about the principles of development of music, development of their abilities, they will learn musical concepts again. He admits that the methodology of music education depends on many factors in the process of education. People's musical culture is formed not only under the influence of school. At home, the surrounding environment, the mass media, and the system of social media as a whole play a big role. There are the following problems in the development of methods of pedagogy development in the development of methods of music education, including:

- *methods of music education, content testing, performance dependence.*
- *development of students' musical and creative abilities.*
- *development of musical ability and voice, age and individual characteristics of music perception.*
- *connection with possibilities of using musical activities in different forms in the development of students.*

The tasks of the methodology include various formation and further development of the educational process, in addition to music lessons, music classes, clubs, holidays, entertainment evenings for classroom and extracurricular activities. The methodology of music education requires the study of literature and visual arts, which are close to the science of music, in

connection with history. This serves as an important tool in the effective implementation of education of students.

The creative activity of students is a leading factor in the implementation of the goals and tasks of music education. Because of mass involvement of students, music science in the school is distinguished from other subjects by its creative activity, artistic and interesting, excitement. Most importantly, creative activity plays an important role in the formation of mental and moral qualities of children. Music stimulates the mind and sharpens the thinking. In music lessons and classes, students learn about education and our national culture and expand their level of knowledge.

In the system of enlightened ideas of one of our great-grandfathers, Abu-Nasr al-Farabi, the purpose and tasks of the role of the art of music in the education of the child and personality are specially recognized. In it, the society of music in human life is noted, and it is said: "*O world of music, it's good that you are here, what would be the condition of a person if you were not there?*" Abu Ali ibn Sina's musical educational views also describe music as a powerful tool that affects the spiritual and physical cultural nature of a person. The idea is put forward that it is necessary to educate a child's sense of music from a very young age, which will strengthen his mental state.

In the well-known book "*Laws of Medicine*", two things should be used to strengthen the child's client. One is rocking the child slowly, and the other is a musical lullaby that has become a habit for putting the child to sleep. He wrote that depending on the amount of intake of these two, the child's body sometimes has a need for education and soul has a need for music.

Thus, scientists and thinkers tried to apply music not only as a tool that effectively affects people, but also as a separate science according to its essence, goals and tasks in society. As mentioned, it is the basis for the creation of popular folk music pedagogy. Schools of educational methods are developing. At present, the task of educating the individual's spirituality requires raising the quality of music education at school.

Today, the goals and tasks of music and education are extremely important. The goal of music education is to bring up the generation as a young and appreciative cultural person who can inherit our musical heritage and inherit our universal musical heritage. The main task of school music education is to develop the necessary knowledge and practical skills in music, to create the necessary conditions for the musical development of talented students.

Conclusion.

The realization of the goals and tasks of music education directly depends on the music lessons at school. In the concept of music education, music at school has a special importance along with other subjects. In order to improve the quality of music education, it is considered an equal subject at school. This requires the modern student to have a positive attitude to the lessons, to be active in the proper organization and management of the musical activities of the students. Music as a lesson has its own characteristics. Every teacher should know these features.

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